

Kinetics of Iodination of Acetophenones by Conductance Method

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The rate constants for the iodination of acetophenones have been measured for various mono and disubstituted acetophenones by conductance method in 20% aqueous pyridine. Linear plots were obtained by plotting the logarithms of the specific reaction rate ($\log k$) against the logarithms of the dissociation constant ($\log K$) and the dipole moment (μ) against energy of activation (E). From the slope of the regression line fitted to $\log k$ and σ_0 data for m -substituted compounds, the value of ' ρ ' the reaction constant has been calculated at various temperatures. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and resonance interaction energy ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) for various substituents have been determined and the results thus obtained are discussed.

In the present work, the kinetics of iodination of acetophenones was studied by conductance method using 20 per cent pyridine as the solvent. Interrelated problems connected with the parameters of the Arrhenius equation have been studied. The applicability of the Hammett Equation¹ has also been investigated. From the slope of the regression line fitted to $\log k$ and σ_0 data for the m -substituted compounds, the value of ' ρ ' the reaction constant has been calculated at various temperatures. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the resonance interaction energy ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) relating to various substituents have been determined. For the reaction series the differences in the extent of resonance interaction in going from reactant to transition state has been calculated with the help of the free-energy term² $-2.303 RT\rho(\bar{\sigma}-\sigma_0)$ instead of by exaltation values for the substituent constants ($\bar{\sigma}-\sigma_0$), since the former expression would furnish more useful information about the electron distribution in the transition state than the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

The acetophenones were prepared and purified by the method of Rout *et al.*³. Medicinal grade 'AnalaR' pyridine was used without further treatment. Resublimed iodine of analytical grade was used. The method used for rate measurement and calculation of the rate constant was similar to that of Pearson⁴.

1. L. P. Hammett. 'Physical Organic Chemistry', Mc.Graw Hill, New York, 1940, p. 193.
2. H. Van Bekkum, P. E. Verkade and B. M. Wepster, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1959, **78**, 815.
3. M. K. Rout, P. L. Nayak and L. N. Patnaik, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 668.
4. R. G. Pearson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 3100.

DISCUSSION

The mechanism of the iodination of acetophenones in 20 per cent pyridine solution has been represented as follows :

Of these, step (1) is the slowest and is rate determining. Thus the reaction rate of the ketone with pyridine and iodine is independent of the halogen concentration and depends upon the usual base catalysed enolisation of the ketone⁴.

On the basis of the above mechanism, the reaction of acetophenone and its derivatives with iodine depends upon the ease of deprotonation at the $-\text{CH}_3$ group adjacent to $> \text{C}=\text{O}$ group.

The electron withdrawing substituents in the phenyl nucleus of the acetophenones will aid this deprotonation by facilitating attack at the $-\text{CH}_3$ group and also by stabilising the negative charge in the transition state and will therefore enhance the reaction rate. On the other hand electron donating substituents on the phenyl nucleus of the acetophenone molecule will retard deprotonation at the $-\text{CH}_3$ group and therefore retard the reaction rate. This is in conformity with the experimental results obtained by us.

Relationship between Velocity constant and Dissociation constant of Acetophenones : The values of the dissociation constant ($\log K$) have been plotted against the value of $\log k_{40}$ for different substituted acetophenones. The values of dissociation constant used are those given by Stewart and Yates⁵.

TABLE 1

Values of velocity and dissociation constants of acetophenone and its derivatives

Sl. no.	Name of the substituent in acetophenone	A + log k_{40}	8 + log k
1.	Acetophenone	1.2840	1.85
2.	<i>p</i> -methyl acetophenone	1.2296	2.53
3.	<i>m</i> -chloro acetophenone	1.4186	0.99
4.	<i>m</i> -nitro acetophenone	1.4694	0.38
5.	<i>p</i> -nitro acetophenone	1.6471	0.06

The plot was found to be a straight line. This is understandable since the dissociating power and the rate of the reaction between iodine and acetophenones are closely related.

Relationship between the Energy of Activation and Dipole moment : The plot of the experimental value for the energy of activation (E) against the dipole moment of substituted acetophenones was a straight line. (The dipole moment values used are those reported by Tiganik *et al.*⁶). The linearity of the plot can be explained. The dipole moment of a compound is a measure of the permanent displacement of electrons towards or away from the nucleus. Since the reactivity of a nucleus in those reactions depends upon the availability of electrons at certain points, the two quantities must be related to each other. The linearity of the curve indicates that the activation energy varies linearly with electrostatic potential produced by the substituent at the reaction centre.

TABLE 2

Dipole moment and energy of activation.

Sl. no.	Name of the acetophenone	$\mu \times 10^{18}$	E in K. Cals/mole
1.	<i>p</i> -methyl-	0.39	6.448
2.	<i>m</i> -nitro-	-4.00	9.422
3.	<i>m</i> -chloro-	-1.56	5.066
4.	Acetophenone-	0	8.290

Applicability of Hammett equation : The Hammett equation¹ may be written as

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho\sigma$$

where k and k_0 represents the specific reaction rate for substituted and unsubstituted compounds respectively.

' ρ ' — the reaction constant

' σ ' — the substitution constant.

The value of correlation coefficient (r) is given by an equation.

$$r = \frac{\Sigma xy - n\bar{x}\bar{y}}{\sqrt{[\Sigma x^2 - nx^2][\Sigma y^2 - ny^2]}}$$

where, $x = \sigma$, $y = \log k$

$\bar{x}$ = the mean value of all σ values.

$\bar{y}$ = the mean value of all $\log k$ values, and

n = number of reactions for which ' r ' is calculated.

The two variable quantities can have maximum correlation of unity. A positive and negative sign indicates the direction of variation, whereas the value of the correlation coefficient gives the magnitude of the variation. Hence a straight line plot of two such variables can be justified from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient.

A regression line was fitted to $\log k$ values against σ_0 values⁷ for the m -substituted compounds at each temperature. The reaction constant (ρ), correlation coefficient (r) and intercept with the ordinate ($\log k_0$) are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

The values of ρ , r and $\log k_0$ from the plot of $\log k$ and σ_0 data for the iodination of acetophenones.

Temperature in °C	' ρ '	r	$4 + \log k_0$
30	+0.2850	0.983	1.0984
35	+0.2570	0.979	1.1590
40	+0.2250	0.992	1.2840

' ρ ' is observed to vary inversely as the temperature thus indicating that the reaction series is isoentropic⁸. As expected, the value of ' ρ ' was found to be positive confirming that the reaction rate must be enhanced by electron withdrawing groups on the phenyl nucleus of the acetophenones.

Considering several reaction series and numerous data it has been suggested by Van Bekkum *et al*². that in those cases where a substituent enters into mesomeric para interaction with the reaction centre, a multiplicity of (exalted) σ values is observed. This holds for $+M$ as well as for $-M$ substituents. But in the absence of the mesomeric para interaction σ values are reasonably constant. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) were calculated from the expression

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\log k - \log k_0}{\rho}$$

7. W. R. Taft, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1805.

8. A. Fischer and J. Vaughan, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 976.

The free-energy ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) difference terms have been calculated for evaluation of the mesomeric para interactions as the effective ' σ ' values ($\bar{\sigma}$) were not considered suitable criteria for the purpose.

$$\Delta\Delta F_p = -2.303RT \rho (\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0)$$

This expression involves not only the exaltation of σ but ρ and T as well. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the corresponding resonance energy differences ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4

Effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and resonance interaction energy differences for the iodination of acetophenones.

Substituent	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
$\bar{\sigma}$	-0.1873	-0.0653	+0.2126	+1.429
$\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0$	-0.067	+0.095	+0.0574	+0.609
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ K.cals/mole	-0.0377	+0.0266	-0.0798	-0.242

It is evident from the above result that the effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) for the ketone series differs from σ_0 only in the case of the *p*-nitrophenyl group. It is true that in view of the relatively large error in the effective σ values resulting from the small value of ρ , one can not rule out the possibility of some resonance interaction in the transition state between electron donating substituents and the developing enolate double bond.

The transition state for the base catalysed iodination is intermediate between the ketone and the enolate ion as shown below :

In the transition state the bond between the methylene group and the carbonyl group develops enol double bond character and this double bond gets into direct conjugation with *p*-nitro group. Thus the resonance interaction of the *p*-nitro group is enhanced in the manner shown below.

This increased resonance is possible only in the transition state but not in the ketone in which the bond in question can not assume double bond character. The negative sign (and also the magnitude) of the resonance interaction energy values also confirm that there is greater para resonance interaction in the transition state than in the ketone state.

On the basis of the above transition state it is also easily understandable why nitro group accelerates the reaction and methoxy group retards the reaction. The nitro group is rate accelerating because in the transition state it withdraws electron from the developing enol bond and thus facilitates deprotonation in the $-\text{CH}_3$ group. On the other hand, the methoxy group retards deprotonation by increasing electron density at the $-\text{CH}_3$ group.

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